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PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF HEART-COMPONENT PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN O'TKIR HOSHIMOV'S NOVEL "BETWEEN TWO DOORS".

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Abstract. This article examines the pragmatic analysis of phraseological units containing the component *heart* in O'tkir Hoshimov's novel "*Between Two Doors*" (*Ikki Eshik Orasi*). Particular attention is paid to the writer's skillful use of heart-related expressions and their role in revealing the individual characteristics and inner world of the characters. Furthermore, the study focuses on important issues such as the ability of heart-based phraseological units to convey both positive and negative emotional and psychological states. The article highlights the pragmatic functions of these phraseological expressions in enhancing the artistic and communicative impact of the literary text.

Keywords: phraseological units, heart component, pragmatics, pragmatic analysis, literary text, O'tkir Hoshimov, *Between Two Doors*, character portrayal, emotional expression, psychological state, phraseology, linguistic analysis.

Speech communication is a complex sphere through which every individual expresses their identity. In the process of verbal communication, a person aims either to convey certain information or to receive information. At the same time, every message reflects the speaker's evaluative attitude toward the subject being discussed.

In literary works, phraseological units serve as important linguistic elements that reflect a nation's worldview, culture, and emotional experiences. Among phraseological expressions associated with human body parts, those containing the component *heart* occupy a special place. Since ancient times, the heart has been regarded as a symbolic concept closely connected with human emotions, spirituality, and inner feelings. Therefore, phraseological units involving the word *heart* are significant not only semantically but also pragmatically.

The national and cultural specificity of a language is clearly manifested in fixed comparisons and phraseological expressions. In his article entitled "*Comparisons as a Product of Figurative National Thinking*," Professor Nizomiddin Mahmudov demonstrates the distinctive ways in which different nations perceive the world through language by examining fixed comparisons in various languages.

The pragmatic analysis of literary discourse studies the use of linguistic units in speech, their purpose, impact, and communicative functions. Heart-component phraseological units are actively employed to express a person's emotional state,

influence the listener or reader, and create emotional and expressive meanings. In revealing the essence of literary works, pragmatic analysis plays an invaluable role.

In Uzbek linguistics, theoretical views related to pragmalinguistics, one of the major branches of linguistics, occupy an important place. From the last quarter of the twentieth century, the need for pragmalinguistic research began to emerge in Uzbek linguistics. As a result, alongside syntactic-semantic studies, the foundations of a pragmalinguistic approach were established. In this regard, the initial studies devoted to presupposition by A. Nurmonov and N. Mahmudov can be regarded as pioneering works in this field.

It is well known that language performs a number of important functions in society. One of its primary functions is the emotional-expressive function. Any literary text not only informs readers about certain events and phenomena but also possesses the power to influence them emotionally. Readers rejoice together with the characters and share in their sorrows. Literary works directly affect human emotions, fostering such values as kindness, loyalty, compassion, and honesty. At the same time, they demonstrate how destructive vices such as evil, betrayal, theft, and cruelty can be for humanity.

While analyzing the heart-component phraseological units used in O'tkir Hoshimov's novel "*Between Two Doors*" (*Ikki Eshik Orasi*), we once again became convinced of the validity of the above-mentioned ideas. The heart-related expressions in the novel play a significant role in revealing the psychological state of the characters, highlighting their unique personalities and speech characteristics.

For analytical purposes, these phraseological units were divided into two groups:

1. Phraseological units expressing negative emotional and psychological states.
2. Phraseological units expressing positive emotional and psychological states.

Heart-component phraseological units are widely used to reveal a person's inner world and to express changes in their psychological state. For example, in O'tkir Hoshimov's novel "*Between Two Doors*" (*Ikki Eshik Orasi*), such expressions are employed to portray Umar Zakunchi's feelings toward Ra'no.

1. The Meaning of Suffering

"Although I did not go to see anyone else off, I went to Shomurod's house. My heart was burning like a glowing ember, yet I did not even turn back to look at Ra'no. To tell the truth, that day I felt sorry for Ra'no's elderly mother." (Hoshimov O'. *Ikki Eshik Orasi*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi Publishing House, 2018. P. 266).

In this passage, the phraseological unit "my heart was burning" is used. This expression is not included in the Explanatory Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language. Its meaning is close to such expressions as "one's heart aches" or "one's heart feels distressed." The use of a simile together with the phraseological unit significantly enhances its emotional impact and expressive power.

2. The Meaning of Fear

"What? What is this witch saying?!"

My heart was pounding violently as I jumped to my feet. At that very moment, she pulled my arm with such force that I groaned as though a spear had pierced my right side and fell onto my side. A foul smell struck my nose."* (Hoshimov O‘., p. 291).

In the above passage, the expression “my heart was pounding violently” conveys Robiya’s intense fear. Instead of simply stating that the character was frightened, the author uses a phraseological expression to vividly portray the feeling of fear and make the character’s emotional state more tangible for the reader.

3. The Meaning of Compassion and Regret

"The late Ochil was a good man. When I remembered that he had once sent matchmakers to Robiya, my heart ached like salt on a wound. What could I do? Kimsan and Robiya had fallen in love with each other, and there was little we could do about it." (Hoshimov O‘., p. 306).

Through the phraseological unit “my heart ached like salt on a wound,” the writer intensifies the feeling of compassion and regret. Here, the author deliberately avoids the more ordinary expression “my heart hurt” and instead chooses the phraseological unit “one’s heart aches like salt on a wound,” thereby enhancing the artistic expressiveness of the text.

4. The Meaning of Anxiety and Panic

‘Hey,’ he said in a lowered voice. ‘Pick them quickly, all right? If the watchman comes, give a whistle!’

Panic entered my heart. So, the walnut tree belongs to the watchman! If he finds out, he’ll kill us!"* (Hoshimov O‘., p. 382).

In this example, the fear experienced by the young character Muzaffar is expressed through a phraseological unit. According to the Explanatory Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language, the expression “panic entered one’s heart” is synonymous with phraseological units such as “turmoil entered one’s heart,” “to fill one’s heart with anxiety,” and “one’s heart fluttered with fear” (Rahmatullayev Sh., p. 274).

As can be seen, the author extensively employs heart-component phraseological units to reveal the characters’ personalities, express their psychological states, and influence the reader’s emotions through both positive and negative connotations. Moreover, compared with individual lexical units, phraseological expressions possess stronger stylistic coloring and emotional intensity, which significantly enhances their ability to reach the reader’s heart and increase the artistic impact of the literary work.

Reference:

1. Hoshimov O‘. Ikki eshik orasi. – Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 2018. – 544 b.
2. Rahmatullayev Sh. O‘zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug‘ati. – Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 1978. – 405 b.
3. Mahmudov N. Til va nutq masalalari. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2013. – 312 b.

4. Mahmudov N. O‘xshatishlar – obrazli milliy tafakkur mahsuli // O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti. – Toshkent, 2011. – № 3. – B. 12–18.
5. Nurmonov A. Tanlangan asarlar. III jild. Lingvistik pragmatika va nutq nazariyasi. – Toshkent: Akademnashr, 2012. – 368 b.
6. Safarov Sh. Pragmalingvistika. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2008. – 286 b.
7. Yo‘ldoshev B. Badiiy matn va uning lingvopoetik tahlili. – Toshkent: Fan, 2007. – 160 b.
8. Mengliyev B., Xoliyorov O. Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili. – Toshkent: Tafakkur bo‘stoni, 2018. – 560 b.
9. Abdupattoyev M. Frazzeologiya va nutq madaniyati. – Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2016. – 224 b.
10. Hojiyev A. Tilshunoslik terminlarining izohli lug‘ati. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2002. – 164 b.